

FINAL PUBLISHABLE REPORT

Grant Agreement number 20NRM04
 Project short name MetriAQ
 Project full title Metrology for the determination of emissions of dangerous substances from building materials into indoor air

Project start date and duration:		01 June 2021, 36 months
Coordinator: Dr Matthias Richter, BAM		Tel: +49 30 8104 4132 E-mail: matthias.richter@bam.de
Project website address: https://metriag.eu		
Chief Stakeholder Organisation: GEV – Association for the Control of Emissions in Products for Flooring Installation, Adhesives and Building Materials		Chief Stakeholder Contact: Klaus Winkels klaus.winkels@emicode.com
Internal Funded Partners:	External Funded Partners:	Unfunded Partners:
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. BAM, Germany 2. TUBITAK, Turkey 3. VSL, Netherlands 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Eurofins, Denmark 5. FhG, Germany 6. POLITO, Italy 7. VITO, Belgium 8. ZAG, Slovenia 	

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Overview	3
2	Need	3
3	Objectives	3
4	Results	4
4.1	Objective 1: Temporally stable emission reference material (ERM) for QA/QC of the emission test chamber procedure	4
4.2	Objective 2: Gaseous certified reference materials (gCRMs) of indoor air pollutants.....	12
4.3	Objective 3: Validation of newly developed ERM and gCRM.....	14
4.4	Objective 4: Numerical model for the prediction of the emission rate.....	21
5	Impact	23
6	List of publications.....	25

1 Overview

Given that European citizens spend more than 80 % of their time indoors, it is vital to have a healthy indoor environment. To achieve this, the release of harmful substances from building materials and other products used indoors into the air must be minimised. Reliable, accurate, traceable measurements of the emissions are paramount to reach high level consumer protection. For the traceable measurement of emissions of volatile organic compounds (VOC) from such materials, this project has developed candidate emission reference materials (ERM) with defined and almost stable emission profiles, and certified reference gas standards (gCRM), in accordance with the quality control requirements of the emission test chamber procedure described in EN 16516. The project results will support the efforts to minimise the use of building products, that emit dangerous substances, thereby ensuring improved indoor air quality.

2 Need

EU regulation No 305/2011/EU (Construction Products Regulation, CPR) codifies that emissions from building products must be controlled to meet the formulated basic requirements (BR) for construction works. This takes place either on the manufacturer side or in test laboratories accredited under ISO/IEC 17025. EN 16516 prescribes a test procedure for the determination of VOC emissions from construction materials in environmental test chambers whose results are used for the Declaration of Performance (DoP) demanded by the CPR demonstrating conformity with the BR. Furthermore, the test chambers results will be used for the mandatory health-related evaluation of these products, once a harmonised evaluation concept defining emission classes is available in Europe. Comparability between measurement results is fundamentally important, as such, EN 16516 demands verification of the performance of the whole method by comparing against external references and the participation in round robin tests (RRT). For this purpose, both ERM and gCRM are urgently needed.

Findings from studies related to the development of reference materials for emission test chamber measurements often did not consider long-term stability over a time period > 100 hours, in contrast to the standard testing time of 28 days. In previous RRT performed with commercial materials, the relative standard deviations of reproducibility between labs varied from 46 % to 300 %. In addition, a common factor with such approaches is a decreasing emission profile, thus making it difficult to predict the emission rate, which is essential for an external reference. This project met these issues by developing candidate ERMs with reproducible and homogenous emission properties. They are more stable than the first approach of an artificial one on lacquer basis developed in the former EMRP project ENV01 MACPoll and supplemented with a suitable numerical model describing the mass transport inside the material which enables the prediction of the VOC release and allow accurate performance verification of test chambers. In view of the great variety of dangerous substances occurring in indoor air, gCRM containing the compounds of the EN 16516 check standard have been developed.

3 Objectives

The overall goal of this project was to provide reference materials to improve the traceable measurement and characterisation of emissions of VOCs from materials for interior use according to EN 16516 and to provide CEN/TC 351/WG 2 and other standardisation committees related to materials emissions testing with validation data for future revision of their standards. The specific objectives were:

1. To develop an emission reference material (ERM) that contains and releases relevant compounds typically emitted by construction products within the range of the EU-LCI list with a constant emission profile that decreases by less than 10 % over at least 14 days, in order to improve the quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) of the emission test chamber method as described in EN 16516.
2. To develop gaseous certified reference materials (gCRM) of indoor air pollutants for compounds selected from key groups that are relevant for the health-related evaluation of building products as stated in the EU-LCI-list, such as aldehydes, unsaturated aldehydes, cyclic dimethylsiloxanes and glycol compounds.
3. To validate the newly developed ERM and gCRM by investigating the short- and long-term stability, reproducibility, and uncertainty in an inter-laboratory comparison, thereby demonstrating the benefits of the reference materials for the test procedure described in EN 16516.

4. To develop a suitable numerical model for simulating the transport processes inside the ERM and the compound release into test chamber air enabling the prediction of the emissions for each of the selected target VOC. The model should support the customised generation of the ERM. All relevant process parameters affecting the release of the compounds from the material will be determined.
5. To contribute to the standards development work of the technical committees CEN/TC351 WG2 and ISO/TC146 SC6 to ensure that the outputs of the project are aligned with their needs, communicated promptly to those developing the standards and to those who will use them (e.g., test chamber operators and gas standards manufacturers), and in a form that can be incorporated into the standards at the earliest opportunity.

4 Results

These are the results of joint collaborative work.

4.1 Objective 1: Temporally stable emission reference material (ERM) for QA/QC of the emission test chamber procedure

The basis for ensuring that the emission reference material (ERM) can have an emission profile that is as constant as possible are reservoir materials that release the target component with a delay. Two approaches were pursued in the MetriAQ project for their development: 1) encapsulation of the components according to the core-shell principle, and 2) high-pressure impregnation of porous materials with the target substance.

Preparation of microcapsules filled with VOC

Fraunhofer IMM (FhG) have synthesized polymer-based microcapsules loaded with various pre-selected volatile organic compounds (VOC), such as D-limonene, alpha-pinene, toluene, *n*-hexane, and *n*-hexadecane through interfacial polyaddition/polycondensation at the oil-water droplet's interface. The process and chemical reactions are schematically shown in **Figure 1**. For the shell formation, hydrophilic monomers such as glycerine, 1,6-hexanediol, hexane-1,6-diamine and carboxymethyl cellulose sodium salt were used. Isophorone diisocyanate (IPDI), toluene 2,4-diisocyanate (TDI) and TUBASSIST®FIX 157W (solvent-free product based on hexamethylene diisocyanate oligomers, CHT R. BEITLICH GmbH) were tested as crosslinker. The droplets were generated using membrane emulsification, employing a microporous membrane (with 5.1 μm und 9.9 μm pore size) composed of Shirasu porous glass (SPG).

Figure 1. Schematic representation of VOC encapsulation through interfacial polyaddition/polycondensation reaction.

It was the aim to obtain microcapsules with two different average diameters, i.e., 15 μm and 50 μm . Smaller capsules have much better mechanical properties compared to larger capsules, but the content of encapsulated VOCs is higher in a large capsule. Depending on the VOC and its properties as to density, miscibility with water and isocyanate(s), as well as interfacial VOC/water tension, the optimization of the synthesis parameters had to be done for each VOC. The effect of crosslinker(s), surfactant type and monomers ratio were investigated using D-limonene and toluene as model substances. For large size capsules, the use of TDI (which is more reactive compared to IPDI) has led to better results, which means that droplets/capsules more stable and more homogeneous in size were obtained. The use of higher amounts of monomers has resulted in capsules with a thicker shell. However, no significant influence on the emission rate was observed.

The obtained capsules were characterized in terms of colloidal stability, particle size, morphology, encapsulation yield, chemical composition, and capsules' shell porosity. For these investigations, FhG and TUBITAK have employed scanning electron microscopy (SEM), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) analysis, and solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy.

Some selected SEM images of limonene-loaded capsules are shown in **Figure 2**. Both intact and burst particles were observed after exposure to the high vacuum conditions required for SEM imaging, confirming their hollow nature. The shell thickness mainly depends on the amount and type of used chemicals.

Figure 2. SEM images of D-limonene-loaded polymer capsules, obtained with different hydrophilic monomers: A and B: glycerine (GTIL_1 and GTIL_110); C: hexane-1,6-diamine (HDTTL_143).

The chemical composition of the shell was confirmed by FTIR analysis. The FTIR spectra of some selected D-limonene- and toluene-loaded capsules after different storage times are presented in **Figure 3**. The presence of functional groups that belong to polyurethane, polyurea and respective VOC can be clearly observed. The presence of non-reacted isocyanate groups could be seen on the FTIR spectra of the GTIL_1 sample after 1 day of drying, but after 15 days all groups were reacted.

Figure 3. FTIR spectra of limonene-loaded capsules GTIL_1 (left) and toluene-loaded capsules synthesized using hexane-1,6-diamine as hydrophilic monomer HDTT_2 (right) after drying at 50°C for different time periods.

Parallel to the FTIR analysis, TGA measurements were performed with the capsule samples. Comparing the TGA results of samples dried for different periods allows to estimate the amount of VOC within the capsules.

Figure 4 shows TGA curve (blue line) of GTIL_1 microcapsule sample.

Figure 4. TGA curve of GTIL_1 sample after 1 day of drying at 50 °C.

It reveals five distinct breakpoints of the mass loss. The first region, denoted by red dots, spans from 30 to 120 °C and exhibits a mass loss of ~10 %, which could be attributed to the presence of water. The second region, indicated by green dots, displays a significant mass loss of about 54 % at 120–173 °C, which corresponds to D-limonene evaporation. The initial decomposition temperature of the polymer shell was about 200 °C and it was completely decomposed at 500 °C. The polymer decomposes in several stages: the hard segments decompose between 200 and 400 °C and the soft segments between 400 and 500 °C. The residual mass is below 5 %. From the TGA results, the encapsulated amount of VOC was estimated for all colloiddally stable capsules, and the amount of VOC varied between 60 % and 70 %, depending on the amount and type of reactants used.

All produced capsule types were tested as to their emission rate (ER) over time to identify the most promising ones. The capsule samples were provided in the form of aqueous suspensions. Before testing is conducted,

usually one millilitre of suspension was transferred into a petri dish. The petri dish was then placed into an emission test chamber.

According to EN 16516, the chamber parameters were set at a temperature of 23 ± 1 °C, a relative humidity (RH) of 50 ± 5 % and an air exchange rate of 0.5 h^{-1} . Different chamber sizes were used, but most of the experiments were conducted in 22 L desiccators. The ER was used to compare different experiments to each other as it normalises the chamber air concentration on the dimension of the sample (or its in-weight or concentration) and air exchange rate (**Equation 1**).

$$ER \left[\frac{\mu\text{g}}{\text{h} \times \text{g}} \right] = \frac{c_{VOC} \left[\frac{\mu\text{g}}{\text{m}^3} \right] \times \text{air exchange rate} \left[\frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{h}} \right]}{m_{ERM} [\text{g}]}, \tag{1}$$

where c_{VOC} is the concentration of the target VOC in the test chamber air and m_{ERM} is the in-weight mass of the ERM material.

Best results have been obtained for capsules filled with D-limonene over a test duration of up to 60 days (1440 hours) (**Figure 5**).

Figure 5. Plots of duplicate emission testings of GTIL_1 (A), HDTIL_120A (B), HDTTL_143 (C) and HDTTL_133A (D).

The best and quite reproducible result was obtained for GTIL_1 (5 % change in emission over 14 days with 270 $\text{ng/g}\cdot\text{h}$; **Figure 5**, A). The duplicate samples of HDTIL_120A exhibit an increase after the initial phase of

emission. After a second, local maximum (~550 h), the emission starts to decrease again, reaching a more stable phase than before (1000–1400 h; 14 % decrease of emission over 14 days; **Figure 5, B**). The most reproducible and also stable emission profile was obtained by testing HDTTL_143 (10 % change in emission over 14 days with 620 ng/g*h; **Figure 5, C**). HDTTL_133A exhibits the worst reproducibility – the values were 6 % decrease and 53 % increase respectively over 14 days, whereas the last two respective datapoints have a significant impact (**Figure 5, D**).

Nonetheless, very good to good results were found (GTIL_1 and HDTTL_143) or indicated (HDTTL_133A). These sample types were considered for further tests in Objective 3 (validation).

Development of VOC reservoirs based on porous materials

For the second approach, porous materials were impregnated with VOC. For the preparation, the materials are placed in an autoclave together with the VOC (**Figure 6**). The reaction vessel is sealed, and CO₂ is introduced until a certain pressure is reached. Then the autoclave is heated to 32 °C – due to the increase in temperature, the pressure rises accordingly to about 74 bar. At these conditions, CO₂ is in its supercritical state and acts as a solvent for the VOC. The mixture inside the autoclave is stirred and the porous material is treated for a few minutes. Then the pressure and/or temperature is slowly reduced. The impregnated material can be removed from the autoclave and transferred into an emission test chamber for testing. Emission testing and data handling (i.e., calculation of emission rate, **Equation 1**) was performed as described above.

Figure 6. Set-up for the preparation of impregnated porous materials.

The impregnation procedure can be effectively conducted without the presence of water, allowing for the treatment of both hygroscopic and non-hygroscopic materials. However, special consideration must be given to hygroscopic materials due to their sensitivity to water, which can negatively impact the material's emission behavior. Dry testing conditions must be established to ensure accurate results when testing hygroscopic materials.

Porous materials (different zeolites, activated carbons, a MOF, and an aerogel) were purchased (**Table 1**). At the beginning, the zeolite FD-107 and the VOC *n*-heptane were used as a model to optimize impregnation parameters, with various factors such as temperature, pressure, impregnation time and several smaller adaptations (influence of material form [powder vs. granules], CO₂ vs. N₂, dry testing vs. humid testing etc.) being investigated. Though the high variability in the results hampers the interpretability, no significant effects were found for any parameters besides humidity for hygroscopic materials. The lack of repeatability suggests that there may be an unknown influential parameter that needs to be identified and controlled. Water ingress can be excluded as similar findings were obtained for non-hygroscopic materials. Overall, the impregnation method was not altered following the optimization process.

Table 1. Porous materials and material parameters used in the study.

#	Material type	Commercial name	pore volume [cm ³ /g]	Median pore size [nm]	Surface area [m ² /g]	Si/Al	Zeolite type
1	Hygroscopic zeolite	FD-107	0.205 ^b	0.67 ^b	462 ^b	1.6	Y
2	Hygroscopic zeolite	13X APG	0.219 ^b	0.644 ^b	603 ^b	1.5	X
3	Hygroscopic zeolite	3A EPG	-	aperture (~0.3 nm) too small, not measureable with the herein used technique ^c	-	1.4	A
4	Non-hygroscopic zeolite	H-BEA-150	0.217 ^b	0.62 ^b	0.612 ^b	150	H
5	Non-hygroscopic zeolite	MFI	-	-	-	>800	NH ₄
6	Activated carbon	A8x30	-	-	-	-	-
7	Activated carbon	C 40/4	0.333 ^b	0.87 ^b	1139 ^b	-	-
8	Activated carbon	C 45/4	0.324 ^b	0.67 ^b	1019 ^b	-	-
9	Activated carbon	C 47/4	0.317 ^b	0.84 ^b	978 ^b	-	-
10	MOF	ZIF-8	0.663 ^a	1.16 ^a	1947 ^a	-	-
11	Aerogel	Aerogel	-	-	-	-	-

^a Taken from literature [Park KS, Ni Z, Cote AP, et al. Exceptional chemical and thermal stability of zeolitic imidazolate frameworks. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*. 2006;103(27):10186-10191], ^b sample measured with argon at 87 K, surface area calculated using BET, pore volume and median pore width calculated using Horvath-Kawazoe (carbons) and Saito-Foley (zeolites), ^c pore size according to producer.

Selected results of the material/VOC screening are summarised in **Table 2**. It was found for dry air measurements, that the hygroscopic materials FD-107 and 13X APG fulfil the stability requirement of less than 10 % change over 14 days, when impregnated with *n*-hexane, *n*-heptane and toluene (**Table 2**, entry 1–5). FD-107 and 13X APG are quite similar to each other (**Table 1**, entry 1–2). The duplicate measurement of toluene impregnated 13X APG deviates, which might be an outlier due to the high variability of the impregnation method (**Table 2**, entry 6). It was not possible to successfully impregnate hygroscopic zeolite 3A EPG, as the pore size of 0.3 nm is too small for the tested VOCs (**Table 1**, entry 3). The tested aerogel showed an emission during the very first days of testing, which quickly decreased to zero. The pore size of the tested aerogel is probably too large, so that any VOC sticking to the surface is quickly evaporated.

As indicated above, hygroscopic materials do not yield an emission in humid testing conditions (**Table 2**, entry 16–18). Non-hygroscopic materials such as non-hygroscopic zeolites, activated carbons, or the MOF, can be impregnated and showed similar results under dry and wet testing conditions (**Table 2**, entry 7–15 and entry 19–48). Most material/VOC combinations show mediocre results in humid air. However, two combinations (BEA/*n*-hexadecane and C 40/4/*n*-hexadecane) showed very good (Δ ER of 1–10 %, **Table 2**, entry 27) to good (Δ ER of 2–34 %, **Table 2**, entry 37) results, respectively. The validation (Objective 3) proved that some material/VOC combinations have a very good in-batch reproducibility and can be used as ERMs even without the stability requirement.

Table 2. Selected results of the material/VOC screening in dry and humid air. The hygroscopic zeolite 3A EPG and aerogel did not show any emission during dry or humid emission testing > 3 days after loading the emission test chamber.

	Entry	Commercial name	Target compound	Δ ER [%] over 14 days	Emission rate [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\cdot\text{g}$] at day 14	No. of samples
				Min–Max	Min–Max	
dry air testing	1	FD-107	<i>n</i> -heptane	5–33	0.6–10	12
	2	FD-107	<i>n</i> -hexane	5–18	3–25	4
	3	FD-107	toluene	5–53	2–15	7
	4	13X APG	<i>n</i> -heptane	5–47	0.2–26	20
	5	13X APG	<i>n</i> -hexane	5–31	2.5–11	5
	6	13X APG	toluene	40–48	1–2.4	2
	7	H-BEA-150	<i>n</i> -heptane	28–37	15–19	2
	8	C 40/4	<i>n</i> -heptane	32–34	33–42	2
	9	C 40/4	<i>n</i> -hexane	16–39	32–37	2
	10	C 40/4	toluene	35–40	53–57	2
	11	C 45/4	<i>n</i> -heptane	29	40	1
	12	C 45/4	toluene	16–32	32–49	2
	13	C 47/4	<i>n</i> -heptane	15–38	4–45	2
	14	C 47/4	toluene	32–33	40–45	2
	15	ZIF-8	<i>n</i> -heptane	34–44	20–55	4
Humid air testing	16	FD-107	<i>n</i> -heptane	-	0	5
	17	FD-107	toluene	-	0	1
	18	13X APG	toluene	-	0	3
	19	H-BEA-150	<i>n</i> -heptane	30–35	10–14	2
	20	H-BEA-150	<i>n</i> -hexane	21–38	18–41	16
	21	H-BEA-150	toluene	16–42	14–33	14
	22	H-BEA-150	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	21–41	13–42	11
	23	H-BEA-150	butyl acetate	-	0	2
	24	H-BEA-150	butyl glycol	30–39	33–237	3
	25	H-BEA-150	cyclohexanone	35–42	25–52	3
	26	H-BEA-150	2-ethoxyethanol	35–48	23–59	3
	27	H-BEA-150	<i>n</i> -hexadecane	1–10	17–95	3
	28	H-BEA-150	methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK)	28–39	14–35	3
	29	C 40/4	<i>n</i> -heptane	14–41	27–61	3
	30	C 40/4	<i>n</i> -hexane	22–40	13–77	20
	31	C 40/4	toluene	26–33	21–104	30
	32	C 40/4	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	24–39	10–39	12

Entry	Commercial name	Target compound	Δ ER [%] over 14 days	Emission rate [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\cdot\text{g}$] at day 14	No. of samples
			Min–Max	Min–Max	
33	C 40/4	butyl acetate	30–35	67–85	2
34	C 40/4	butyl glycol	25–30	18–107	2
35	C 40/4	cyclohexanone	39–41	28–31	2
36	C 40/4	2-ethoxyethanol	38–39	66–71	3
37	C 40/4	<i>n</i> -hexadecane	2–34	11–17	2
38	C 40/4	methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK)	35–39	22–76	3
39	C 45/4	<i>n</i> -heptane	24–45	32–38	3
40	C 45/4	<i>n</i> -hexane	41–42	34–59	2
41	C 45/4	toluene	15–50	26–108	6
42	C 45/4	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	32	28	1
43	C 47/4	<i>n</i> -heptane	24–44	28–34	3
44	C 47/4	<i>n</i> -hexane	21–35	13–37	6
45	C 47/4	toluene	25–39	15–71	3
46	C 47/4	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	37–46	18–22	2
47	ZIF-8	<i>n</i> -heptane	30–37	28–41	2
48	ZIF-8	<i>n</i> -hexane	58	16	1

Key outputs and conclusions (Objective 1)

For the ERM reservoir materials, capsule types containing D-limonene were obtained that are usable under the standardised test conditions prescribed in EN 16516. Depending on the best suited shell material (GTIL1 and HDTTL_143), stable emission profiles within 5–10 % decrease over 14 days were achieved. The knowledge obtained here is a good basis for the development of further encapsulated VOC for which the shell composition must be individually chosen.

The impregnated activated carbon did not show such a good stability in terms of the emission profile in humidified air but the in-batch reproducibility is very good so that these materials would be good suited for e.g., round robin tests. At least one material/VOC combination (BEA/*n*-hexadecane) showed a decrease of less than 10 % over 14 days in humid air. For dry air applications at least three porous material/VOC combinations (FD-107 or 13X APG/*n*-hexane, *n*-heptane or toluene) provide stable emission profiles in terms of the objective goals.

With the development of the ERM the aims of Objective 1 were achieved.

4.2 Objective 2: Gaseous certified reference materials (gCRMs) of indoor air pollutants

Volatile Organic Compounds relevant for indoor air quality

Most commercial gas standards of indoor-relevant compounds are not certified due to a lack of primary reference materials to which the MetrIAQ project aims to contribute. Therefore, VSL and VITO developed gaseous primary reference materials (gPRM) and gaseous certified reference materials (gCRMs) in this

project. The gPRM and gCRMs are gas-phase standards in high-pressure cylinders or dynamic calibration gas mixtures containing trace levels of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) in nitrogen and air, respectively. To ensure these reference materials are relevant to determine the emissions of dangerous substances from building materials into indoor air, the VOCs were selected based on the check material from paragraph 8.2.2.3 in EN 16516 which describes the checks on analytical system performance. The analytical performance can be evaluated using a check material. This is a chromatographic test mix containing VOCs that are representative of the range of compounds of interest for indoor air quality. The EN 16516 check material contains at least *n*-hexane (CAS No. 110-54-3), Methyl Iso Butyl Ketone (MIBK, CAS No. 108-10-1), toluene (CAS No. 108-88-3), butyl acetate (CAS No. 123-86-4), cyclohexanone (CAS No. 110-82-7), *o*-xylene (CAS No. 95-47-6), phenol (CAS No. 143-74-8), 1,2,3-trimethylbenzene (1,2,3-TMB, 526-73-8) and *n*-hexadecane (CAS No. 544-76-3). The composition of the check material was adjusted, 1,2,3-trimethylbenzene was replaced by 1,3,5-trimethylbenzene (1,3,5-TMB, CAS No. 108-67-8) and *n*-hexadecane was not used. It is difficult to purchase or obtain 1,2,3-TMB with a purity above 90 %. This has consequences for the reference material production and the measurements performed with the reference materials. If the purity of the starting material is not considered, there will be a bias in the analytical measurement results. Furthermore, when using the analytical column (5 % phenyl / 95 % methyl polysiloxane capillary column) prescribed by EN 16516, 1,3,5-TMB coelutes with phenol. One of the impurities in 1,2,3-TMB is 1,3,5-TMB, so the phenol peak in the chromatogram would partly consist of 1,3,5-TMB which also gives a bias in the analytical measurement result. When working with highly pure starting materials, the bias will be smaller. The 1,3,5-TMB isomer can be purchased with a high purity of $\geq 98\%$. The VOC *n*-hexadecane is omitted from the gPRM and gCRM as this compound, with a boiling point of 287 °C and vapour pressure of 0.0025 kPa, cannot be produced as a gas mixture in a cylinder.

Preparing gPRMs and gCRMs

The static gPRMs are gas mixtures of the VOCs in nitrogen in high-pressure cylinders prepared according to ISO 6142-1. These are prepared by injection of a liquid VOC mixture into a high-pressure cylinder. Two dilutions were required to achieve a mixture of 50 nmol mol⁻¹ of each VOC in nitrogen. Multiple mixtures at 50 nmol mol⁻¹ were prepared in three types of cylinder treatment to determine the most suitable cylinder treatment.

Next to the *static* gPRMs also *dynamic* gPRMs were developed. These are gas mixtures were prepared using dynamic methods to obtain calibration gas mixtures with VOCs in clean, dry air, according to ISO 6145-4. The method is based on the delivery of a constant mass flow of the liquid VOC mixture through a capillary. The constant mass flow is obtained by applying a constant pressure to the liquid VOC mixture, thereby forcing it through the capillary. Two dilution stages were required to achieve a mixture of 50 nmol mol⁻¹ of each VOC in air.

The gPRM can be sampled onto sorbent tubes to obtain transfer standards in the form of gCRM. According to ISO 16017-1, the gCRM are prepared via pumped sampling onto sorbent tubes of known volumes from both the static and dynamic gPRMs. The sampled tubes were used to develop and validate the analytical method (TD-GC-FID), compare the gPRMs and dynamic standard gas mixture preparation (**Figure 7**), and for the stability study of the gPRMs.

Figure 7. Graphical representation of the results from the verification of the gPRMs, using dynamic standard gas mixtures to calibrate the TD-GC-FID.

Analysis of the static gPRMs, using the dynamic gPRM to calibrate the TD-GC-FID, showed comparable results for most VOCs except for cyclohexanone and phenol. During or after preparation of the static gPRM phenol decomposes, precipitates as a solid and/or absorbs to the cylinder wall.

In addition to the gPRM with VOCs, VSL also developed a set-up and method to prepare gPRMs of formaldehyde in nitrogen in high pressure cylinders. It is not a straightforward procedure to prepare these types of gPRMs as it is not possible to use formaldehyde as a starting material because pure formaldehyde is a polymer, paraformaldehyde. Therefore, paraformaldehyde or 1,3,5-trioxane is used and thermally converted to formaldehyde before mixture preparation. At VSL a set-up was developed to thermally convert 1,3,5-trioxane to formaldehyde. For the thermal conversion a heated line with a length of 2 meters was used. During the project the optimal temperature for the conversion was determined, 99.8 % of the 1,3,5-trioxane was converted to formaldehyde after 3 hours at 240 °C. In the last months of the project several gas mixtures in high pressure cylinders of approximately 1 ppm formaldehyde in nitrogen were prepared. In the future the mixture preparation needs to be validated, by determining the stability of the gas mixtures.

Key outputs and conclusions (Objective 2)

The MetrIAQ project consortium prepared gPRMs and gCRMs with the selected VOCs. The gPRMs were prepared in high pressure cylinders as static gas mixtures and with dynamic preparation methods. Preparation of static gas mixtures with phenol was not possible, during or after preparation phenol decomposes, precipitates as a solid and/or absorbs to the cylinder wall. Fortunately, it is possible to prepare dynamic gas mixtures with phenol. Both the static and dynamic gPRMs can be sampled onto sorbent tubes to obtain gCRMs. The sorbent tubes can be used to calibrate a GC for the determination of these VOC in indoor air.

With the development of the gPRMs and gCRMs the aims of Objective 2 were achieved.

4.3 Objective 3: Validation of newly developed ERM and gCRM

Validation of ERM

Reference materials should be homogeneous, reproducible and stable. With regard to stability, short-term stability, e.g. for the period of transportation to the end user, and long-term stability, which provides information on the durability of the material and optimal storage conditions, must be taken into account. For these

investigations, a set of ERMs was produced by BAM and FhG and distributed between the consortium partners BAM and Eurofins. Batches of impregnated AC C 40/4 (VOC: *n*-hexane; granulate), AC C 45/4 (VOC: toluene; granulate), AC C 40/4 (VOC: 2-ethyl-1-hexanol; granulate) and μ -capsules (VOC: D-limonene; capsule type HDTTL_143) were produced. The batches of impregnated porous materials were split into smaller portions and filled into amber glass vials. Glass petri dishes were filled with aqueous μ -capsule suspension and pre-aged in an emission test chamber (~2 weeks, 23 °C, 0 % RH). Air-tight packages containing each material with a specific mass and number of petri dishes were prepared based on the emission rate of the ERMs and chamber sizes used (119 L and 270 L). The goal was to achieve a target concentration between 50–150 ng/L for each VOC.

Six samples were measured immediately after arrival at BAM and one sample at Eurofins to obtain values for the in-batch repeatability and to have a value without influence of the storage conditions. The other packages were stored for the following times and at temperatures and then measured in emission test chambers according to EN 16516 to investigate the storage stability of the ERMs:

- At 35 °C stored for 14 days and 1 month
- At 23 °C (standard storage conditions) stored for 14 days, 1, 3, 6 and 12 months
- At 5–10 °C stored for 14 days, 1, 3, 6 and 12 months
- At –18 °C stored for 14 days

Samples were taken exactly after 24 h (1 day), 72 h (3 days), 168 h (7 days), 240 h (10 days), 336 h (14 days), 504 h (21 days) and 672 h (28 days) for each chamber test.

The analytical results of the test chamber air were translated into emission rates (ER) according to Equation 1 (section 4.1). For the evaluation, the results of day 28 after loading the ERMs into the emission test chamber were used.

Sample homogeneity

During internal validation, six replicates of the same ERM batches were measured in parallel at BAM. The results are correlated in a sense, that many usually variable parameters were basically the same, such as ambient air pressure, performance of the measurement device or temperature in the laboratory. This reduced the variability of the results to only a few remaining parameters, such as the homogeneity of the materials (**Table 3**). Very good homogeneities were found for the toluene impregnated C 45/4 (granulate) and the D-limonene loaded μ -capsule sample. Mediocre homogeneities were found for the *n*-hexane and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol impregnated C 40/4 (granulate) samples.

Table 3. Results of the in-batch repeatability test. Six replicates of the same ERM batches were measured in parallel. The toluene impregnated C 45/4 (granulate) and the D-limonene loaded μ -capsule sample are highly homogenous. The *n*-hexane and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol impregnated C 40/4 (granulate) samples revealed only mediocre homogeneities.

	<i>n</i> -hexane	toluene	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	D-limonene
average ER [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\cdot\text{g}$]	24.0	36.2	28.2	13.1
standard deviation [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\cdot\text{g}$]	3.5	1.1	5.3	0.9
rel. SD [%]	14.5	3.0	18.6	6.7

Reproducibility and short and long-term stability of the ERMs

No trend was found for any of the storage conditions. High and low values were obtained for short and long storage times [0 (IT-immediate testing), 0.5, 1, 3, 6 and 12 months], as well as for each temperature (-18, 5, 23 and 35 °C) (**Figure 8**).

Figure 8. VOC specific emission rates (ER) of BAM (blue) and Eurofins (orange) for samples stored under different storage conditions. No trend was observed for any storage time or temperature. A gross measurement error occurred at BAM’s measurement of the ‘23°14d’ sample.

Since the storage does not seem to have any influence, the same results were used to calculate the in-batch reproducibility (Table 4). As the testings were conducted at two different laboratories and over 12 months, the evaluation resembles the top-down approach. This way, the reproducibility reveals the variability of the overall emission test chamber procedure. Both partners produced very similar average emission rates and relative standard deviations. The long-term stability test revealed that the ERMs are stable and the in-batch reproducibility is quite good for at least one material/VOC combination, so that large batches of ERM can be produced, characterised, and used for at least 12 months.

Table 4. Results of the in-batch reproducibility (values taken from the investigation of storage conditions). The results of BAM and Eurofins are very similar. The relative standard deviation can be used as a measure for the variability of the overall emission test chamber procedure.

	n-hexane	toluene	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	D-limonene
mean ER [µg/hxg] BAM	21.5	31.2	23.0	9.5
mean ER [µg/hxg] Eurofins	22.4	30.4	19.9	13.2
mean ER [µg/hxg] both	21.9	30.8	21.4	11.4

standard deviation [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$] BAM	5.1	7.0	6.6	4.3
standard deviation [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$] Eurofins	6.5	7.1	7.0	5.8
standard deviation [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$] both	5.7	6.9	6.7	5.3
rel. SD [%] BAM	23.9	22.3	28.5	44.8
rel. SD [%] Eurofins	28.9	23.2	35.1	44.2
rel. SD [%] both	26.2	22.4	31.4	47.0

Since ERMs are no primary reference materials, only the measurement uncertainty can be determined. The validation of ERMs resembles the top-down approach and thus the reproducibility can be used to estimate the uncertainty of the overall procedure (i.e., it includes the uncertainty of the ERM, of the emission test chamber procedure, of the sampling and of the analysis). A differentiation of the individual components is also partially possible but can be quite challenging, in particular the determination of the influence of parameter fluctuation of the emission test chamber. Most parameters were characterised (**Table 5**), but the influence (i.e., the physical-chemical relation and/or sensitivity coefficient) on the ERM is not yet clear for all parameters. In contrast, the uncertainty of sampling ($u \leq 5\%$) can be easily determined and is quite small. The uncertainty of analysis was also determined, and the VOC specific values can be found in **Table 6**.

Table 5. Mean values, standard deviations, and measurement uncertainty (U , $k=2$) of important chamber parameters, when the 1 m^3 chamber is set to standard conditions.

Parameter	Mean value	Standard deviation	U ($k=2$)	Unit
Temperature	23.09	0.004 ^a	0.5 ^c	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
Relative humidity	51.4	0.7 ^b	1.4 ^c	%
Air inlet flow	518.9	4.1	8.2	L/h
Air exchange rate	0.509	0.004	0.008	h^{-1}
Chamber volume	1019.5 ^d	16.1 ^d	32.2 ^d	L
Pressure	1024.4 ^e	19.4 ^e	38.8 ^e	hPa
Air flow over sample	0.2	0.1	0.2	m/s

^a Temperature inhomogeneity = $0.11\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, ^b Relative humidity inhomogeneity = 0.36% , ^c Extended uncertainty type b, ^d Determined by $V = (\text{air inlet flow}/\text{air exchange rate})$, ^e Example for a duration of four days – depends highly on the weather.

Table 6. Repeatability (s_r), reproducibility (s_R), and expanded uncertainty (U , $k=2$) of the TD-GC-FID method at BAM.

VOC	s_r (%)	s_R (%)	U (%)
<i>n</i> -hexane	4.5	4.8	9.6
toluene	1.9	2.7	5.5
2-ethyl-1-hexanol	0.9	5.8	11.5
D-limonene	1.7	1.6	3.1

Validation of gPRM

An important property of reference materials is the stability period. In case of the static gPRM this is the period during which the composition of the gas mixture in a cylinder is stable. To determine the stability of the VOCs in the static gPRMs after preparation, the gPRMs were sampled into sorbent tubes at $t = 2$ weeks, 2 months, 3 months, 7 months, 9 months, 13 months, 19 months and 22 months. After sampling, the tubes were analysed using TD-GC-FID. The GC was calibrated with tubes sampled from the dynamic gPRM. The dynamic gPRM was prepared at the same time as the sorbent tubes were sampled from the static gPRMs. The stability of the

static gPRMs has been tested for 3 different cylinder treatments. In each treatment two mixtures have been prepared and stability was determined (**Figure 9**).

Figure 9. Graphical representation of the stability results for the VOCs in one of the gPRMs. First point in the graph is the gravimetric amount fraction (nmol mol^{-1}). The other points are the calculated amount fractions

based on the measurements. The dotted lines indicate the expanded uncertainty determined for the VOC in the gPRM. Results for all the mixtures can be found in project deliverable D6.

Two methods have been used to determine if the VOCs are stable in the static gPRMs, 1) initial loss; looking at the deviation between the measured amount fraction and the gravimetric amount fraction of the VOCs in the static gPRMs. The VOCs are not stable in the static gPRM if the deviation of one or more stability measurements is larger than the expanded uncertainty and 2) long term instability; if the slope of the interpolation function (calculated using ordinary least squares regression), based on stability measurements, was smaller than two times its associated standard uncertainty the stability measurements show a horizontal trend and no instability (**Table 7**). The results for phenol were not processed, as it was evident from visual inspection of the data that the mixtures were unstable with respect to the amount fraction of this component.

Table 7. Results stability study for the three different cylinder treatments tested.

VOC	Treatment 1		Treatment 2		Treatment 3	
	Initial loss	Long Term Instability	Initial loss	Long Term Instability	Initial loss	Long Term Instability
<i>n</i> -hexane	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	No
MIBK	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No
Toluene	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No
Butyl acetate	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Cyclohexanone	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
<i>o</i> -xylene	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
1,3,5-TMB	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No

All 3 cylinder treatments show initial loss of several VOCs. Treatment 2 shows long term instability for several components, treatment 1 only for *o*-xylene and treatment 3 shows no long-term instability for the VOCs. Based on the results there is initial loss for all treatment types. This could be caused during preparation of the gas mixture or due to absorption to the cylinder wall. Thereafter the gas mixtures are stable for all VOCs when using cylinder type 3. To take the instability into account it was added as an uncertainty source for the uncertainty calculation.

The uncertainty of the reference materials was determined taking into account the preparation and sampling onto sorbent tubes ($U_{prep} = 1\%$, $k = 2$), the calibration using dynamic PRMs ($U_{cal} = 5\%$, $k = 2$), the measurement uncertainty (U_{meas}) and the stability (U_{stab}). U_{meas} and U_{stab} are different for each VOC and for each cylinder treatment used. The uncertainty calculations can be found in project deliverable D3 Annex 4 (<https://zenodo.org/records/8189413>) and in project deliverable D6 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13163378>).

The uncertainty budget for the gPRM has been determined, and relative expanded uncertainties of 5 % have been obtained for gPRMs prepared dynamically. Static gPRMs, in cylinders, have relative expanded uncertainties between 8–16 %. Cylinder treatment 3 shows the best results for the stability, with no long-term instability for the VOCs.

Validation gCRM

The gCRMs in the form of sorbent tubes sampled with VOCs are validated by conducting a short-term stability and storage study. To check the possible influence of storage temperature and the way of packaging on the stability of sampled sorbent tubes sampled with Tenax[®] TA as sorbent material, VITO sampled a total of 48 tubes. During the course of 1 month, these tubes were analysed at certain intervals: immediately after sampling, and then 3, 9, 13, 20 and 28 days after sampling. Twenty-one tubes were stored under regular conditions: in a black plastic box in the lab at room temperature. Six of them were analysed immediately after sampling, and then 3 at each remaining analysis day. Nine tubes were stored in the freezer (-18°C), nine tubes

were stored in the fridge (6°C) and nine tubes were stored at lab temperature, but in a transparent plastic package. These tubes were analysed per 3 on day 3, 13 and 28 (**Figure 10**).

Figure 10. Graphic representation results short term stability study (reg = regular packaging).

By comparing the relative standard deviations (repeatability) throughout the whole experimental set (so including the regulars, and the tested analytical days and storage conditions) with the repeatability of the spiked tubes during the analytical validation process we can conclude that the tested possible effects (storage time and storage place/temperature) have no influence on the analytical result for all the compounds. The gCRM in sorbent tubes can be stored capped with stainless steel caps at room temperature for a period of 28 days.

As both the static and dynamic gPRMs are analysed by sampling the gas mixtures into sorbent tubes to obtain the gCRM, the uncertainty of the gPRM and gCRM are the same.

Interlaboratory comparison gCRM and ERM

To demonstrate the proof of concept, a workshop and an inter-laboratory comparison (ILC) were organised using the gCRM and ERM. The ILC involved 2 parts:

- Part 1: Analysis of gCRMs
- Part 2: Emission test chamber method with ERMs

During the workshop, participants could take samples from a dynamic gas mixture, in the laboratories of project partner VITO, using their own sampling pumps and sorbent tubes. The aim of the workshop was to assess the capability of laboratories to sample and measure VOCs relevant in emissions from building materials. The reference value for the workshop and the results of the participants were processed by VSL. The aim of part 1 of the ILC was 1) to validate the developed gCRM and 2) to assess the capability of laboratories to measure VOC contents relevant for emissions from building materials. For this part VITO sampled the participant sorbent tubes with a dynamic gas mixture containing VOCs in air. The evaluation of the results is performed using zeta scores (ζ) as described in ISO 13528. The reference values were determined by VSL. The aim of part 2 of the ILC was 1) to validate the developed ERM and 2) to assess the capability of laboratories to measure VOC contents released from materials in the emission test chamber procedure. The ERMs are either impregnated porous materials produced by BAM, or μ -capsules filled with VOC produced by FhG. Four VOCs (*n*-hexane, toluene, 2-ethyl-1-hexanol and D-limonene) were used to produce the ERMs. An evaluation of the result obtained including information regarding the repeatability and reproducibility of the data and the major

uncertainty sources in sampling, analysis and reporting of the results can be found in project deliverable D5 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12545048>).

With the use of the gCRM in the ILC part 1 it was shown that this reference material can be used for this application and as a check material according to EN 16516 section 8.2.2.3. These reference materials are traceable to the international standards and therefore primary standards as required by the EN 16516 (section 8.4.2). The results of ILC part 1 highlight the complexity of these measurements, both for the providers and the participants. The results from the labs indicate that one lab performed satisfactorily for all VOCs, the other labs that perform satisfactorily for most VOCs and questionably for a few components. The biased results imply that the participants' uncertainty evaluation did not include all significant sources of uncertainty, as the uncertainty is a parameter in the calculation of the zeta score.

The ERMs were validated in ILC part 2. At least one material (the toluene impregnated C 40/4 powder) performed very well. It has a reasonable emission rate and a low variability of only 18 %. This proves, that the laboratories' emission testing capabilities are generally good at least under less challenging conditions (i.e., reasonable chamber air concentration and toluene is usually easily detectable). Two other materials (*n*-hexane impregnated BEA powder and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol impregnated C 40/4 powder) showed low emission rates and high variabilities. It can be assumed, that parts of these findings are due to the material specific behaviour and due to the low emission rate, while both are mutually dependent on each other. The μ -capsules showed very unsatisfying results, i.e., very low emission and thus only a few valid measurement results were obtained. The participants gave information about their emission testing and measurement methods. Most methods seem to be in good accordance with the standard. The best practice of using mass flow controllers/meters for sampling was used by all participants. However, more emphasis should be on the estimation of uncertainty. It might lead to improvement and higher transparency of the results. It is further advised to adjust the sampling volume in such a way that the estimated VOC concentration in the emission test chamber is within the calibrated range of the analytical system.

Key outputs and conclusions (Objective 3)

Based on the validation and stability study of the ERMs the uncertainty was estimated. Since ERMs are no primary reference materials, only the measurement uncertainty can be determined. The uncertainty is highly dependent on the material/VOC combination and point of time of sampling. Bearing in mind the relatively high uncertainty of the overall procedure, very good in-batch reproducibilities (18 % and 22 % respectively at day 14 after loading) were found for activated carbon C 40/4 and C 45/4 impregnated with toluene. Mixed results were obtained for the batch-to-batch reproducibility, though the in-batch reproducibility seems much more important. Unlike the in-batch reproducibility, the batch-to-batch reproducibility can be circumvented by producing very big batches. The high stability of ERMs enables quite long storage times of up to 12 months, which supports this work-around.

Based on the validation and stability study of the gPRM and gCRM the uncertainty was determined. The relative expanded uncertainties of 5 % have been obtained for gPRMs prepared dynamically. Static gPRMs, in cylinders, have relative expanded uncertainties of 8–16 %.

The workshop and ILC part 1 and part 2 were performed to validate the ERM and gCRM developed in the MetriAQ project. The ILCs showed that the ERM and gCRM are suitable for this use. Based on the results obtained in the ILCs laboratories were able to assess their capabilities to sample and measure VOCs relevant in emissions from building materials. This paved the way to set up similar ILCs using these reference materials in the future. While a few ERMs, loaded with single VOCs, are almost ready for application, further development is needed to broaden the scope for other VOCs.

With the validation of the ERM, gPRM and gCRM and the performance of the ILC the aims of Objective 3 were achieved.

4.4 Objective 4: Numerical model for the prediction of the emission rate

Model for ERM design

POLITO and ZAG developed a simplified model based on the general mass balance of the system emission reference material (ERM) – emission test chamber (EC) and the balance of the VOCs within the ERM. The model was fed with data from the test chamber characterisation (distribution of the temperature and relative humidity, air velocity caused by the ventilator) carried out by BAM, the first ERM prototypes from Objective 1 and a diffusion vial filled with toluene that was placed in a chamber. The Biot number was used as indicator of

the controlling phenomenon within the ERM–EC system. The Biot number is defined as the ratio between the diffusive and convective resistance. With the model it was possible to characterise the used test chambers by Biot number and identify the conditions at which the internal transport was the controlling step. This was useful to identify the best test conditions that led to a concentration profile that reflected the internal ERM transport.

Finite Element Modelling (FEM)

ZAG have adapted the FEM model applied here from the one developed in the previous EMRP project ENV56 KEY-VOCs. It describes the emission of the VOC from the top surface of the ERM into the air/gas layer with the prescribed thickness above the ERM.

Figure 11. Schematic representation of 3D axisymmetric FEM model without CFD.

In this project, the artificial boundary condition with fixed concentration from the previous model was replaced with a new scalar variable $c_{ch}(t)$ – the average concentration of the VOC in the test chamber air. It is not a locally-dependent, but a time-dependent variable, which is taken as the outer boundary condition. This boundary condition is calculated with the implicit equation:

$$n_{VOC,ch}(t) = c_{ERM,0} \cdot V_{ERM} - c_{ERM,ave}(t) \cdot V_{ERM} - \int_0^t n_{VOC,ch}(t') \cdot n_{exch} dt' \quad (2)$$

Where $n_{VOC,ch}$ is the total amount of VOC in the test chamber air in mol, $c_{ERM,0}$ the initial concentration of the VOC in the ERM in mol m⁻³, $c_{ERM,ave}$ the average concentration of the VOC in the ERM in mol m⁻³, V_{ERM} the volume of the sample in m³, n_{exch} the air exchange rate in s⁻¹.

Although the FEM model developed here is a dynamic one that predicts the emission profile over time, the measurand considered for the evaluation is the concentration in the chamber after 7 days, in mol m⁻³. The uncertainty of the measurand was evaluated through an uncertainty budget based on recommendations of the Guide for the Expression of the Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM). The influence quantities considered in the evaluation, together with the source of reference value and uncertainties are explained in detail in deliverable D4 of this project (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12749007>).

It is worth mentioning, that assuming a constant internal diffusion coefficient for the material (D_{mat}) is a simplification that was applicable to the ERM characteristics as expected at the beginning of the project. This was having a homogeneous material with embedded VOC sources inside. The current ERM consists of a free powder with particles that are irregular in shape and size (refer to section 4.1). This translates into different modelling requirements and challenges the application of only one D_{mat} for describing the transport phenomena.

Metrological analysis of the FEM Model

An uncertainty budget was developed by POLITO based on the significant parameters of the FEM model and their respective uncertainties. The propagation of uncertainty was based on the recommendations of Supplement 6 of the GUM.

Key outputs and conclusions (Objective 4)

The influence quantities with the most important contributions to the uncertainty of the FEM prediction for the BEA zeolite–hexane system are the concentration of the sample, the effective diffusion coefficient of the material and the number of air exchanges within the chamber. The concentration of the sample c_o is calculated based on the loading percentage reached during the impregnation process. D_{mat} is currently directly calculated from regression while the n_{Exch} depends on the chamber used during the test. The current distribution of uncertainty can be improved to values comparable with those of the experimental values (25 %) if the uncertainty of D_{mat} is reduced down to 15 % and the concentration c_o decreases down to 6 %. This could be performed by evaluating statistically the uncertainty of D_{mat} over a significant number of regression points (> 104) and by improving the accuracy of the mass of VOC inside the material after impregnation and the measurement of the air flow and volume inside the chambers.

The current model is able to predict the concentration after 7 days with an uncertainty comparable to the level of the experimental values (order of 20 %). To be able to predict the concentration, an effective diffusion coefficient must be available for the specific material–VOC combination. This value can be calculated by the least squares method and implemented over other cases with the same material–VOC combination, independently of the geometry of the sample. Further validation is recommended with different materials, VOCs and test temperatures.

Based on the design experience and the models produced during the development, some recommendations have been developed, intended to facilitate the design of ERM to fit the requirements of different applications. The main recommendations concern the use of smaller chambers (< 200 L) with higher reproducible velocities to maintain a high Biot number (> 1000). This is intended to make the system ERM–EC controlled by ERM internal transport, providing better insight into the dynamic of the material. Other recommendations are referred to the improvement of the model and the uncertainty evaluation and are available in deliverable D4 of this project.

5 Impact

To maximise the impact of the project and ensure a wide dissemination of the knowledge generated, a website has been created and [permanently updated](#). A Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB) with 20 members was set up containing representatives from the EU-LCI working group, indoor emission testing laboratories, labelling schemes, manufacturers of construction products, regulators, and standardisation bodies. News was furthermore posted in the LinkedIn group “VOC measurements”. In total, the consortium have published one paper and submitted two articles to high-ranking scientific journals, participated in 8 conferences and organised training for the stakeholder community in the form of a webinar and a workshop. Any activities undertaken within the project runtime are summarised below.

Impact on industrial and other user communities

The project engaged with industrial and end user communities through the set-up of its Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB). The SAB met twice (16 February 2022 and 08 December 2022) in ordinary meetings and a third time in the context of a webinar on 11 April 2024 entitled *Metrology for Indoor Air Quality – Reference materials for QA/QC of the emission test chamber procedure* which allowed a broader audience of 56–64 persons to learn about and discuss the project results. Apart from that, the project benefitted from the active support of the single SAB members that provided advice or sample material for test purposes.

The relevant industrial user communities were partly involved in the validation of the ERMs and gCRMs developed in this project in terms of training activities and an inter-laboratory comparison. On 18 October 2023, a stakeholder workshop entitled *Metrology for Indoor Air Quality* took place at the premises of project partner VITO in Mol, Belgium. In [total, 14 participants attended the event in person](#). Besides information on the project outcome, [3 participants took the opportunity to take VOC gas samples at VITO’s dynamic preparation line with their own equipment for own QC purposes. The gas standard contained the compounds of the gCRMs. Data obtained from these measurements were furthermore used for the validation work.](#) Shortly after the workshop, the first part of the inter-laboratory comparisons (gCRMs) on the reference products took place. Eight participants including stakeholders took part. Part 2 (ERMs) started later in January 2024. As well, 8 participants including stakeholders took part.

Impact on the metrology and scientific communities

An important finding from the project was that the reservoir materials required for stable ERMs must be optimised specifically for each VOC. The project demonstrated the feasibility of this and showed ways in which NMIs/DIs can adopt the methodology and extend their portfolio of reference materials. Further development by institutes outside the MetrIAQ consortium is important, as the original plans to commercialise the ERM have been thwarted by a change in BAM's thematic focus. Nonetheless, BAM plans to use the ERMs to organise an international RRT for the emission test chamber method according to EN 16516 and ISO 16000-9 on next possible occasion. Further to this, VSL intends to develop new calibration services on the project's development of dynamic and static reference materials.

The partners in this consortium are actively involved in the CCQM Gas Analysis Working Group (GAWG) and in EURAMET Metrology in Chemistry Technical Committee (TC-MC) and the outputs from this project were presented to them. The successful development of gPRMs and gCRMs will support the organisation of future Key Comparisons organised by the CCQM-GAWG and EURAMET TC-MC and will allow new calibration and measurement capability claims in the field of indoor air and VOC analysis. The gained know-how can be used by the scientific community and by other reference material providers for the preparation of similar calibration standards.

One paper on research results achieved during the project was already published and two further papers have been submitted for publication in high impact peer-reviewed scientific journals. As mentioned above, a workshop and an online webinar on the preparation of traceable and accurate gCRMs and ERMs was held, to which representatives of industry (both manufacturers and users), academic, standardisation and users were invited. POLITO have implemented project findings in educational courses at bachelor and master levels in architecture and mining engineering to promote young academics.

Project results were presented at 8 national and international conferences, e.g., the 36th European Colloid & Interface Society Conference (4-9 September 2022, Crete, Greece), the 10th International Symposium on modern principles of air monitoring and biomonitoring (Airmon) (7-10 November 2022, Bristol, United Kingdom), 21st International Metrology Congress (CIM) (7-10 March 2023, Lyon, France), the 18th Healthy Buildings 2023 Europe Conference (11-14 June 2023, Aachen, Germany), and the GAS Analysis 2024 (30 January – 1 February 2024, Paris, France).

Impact on relevant standards

The project aimed to provide impact for all standards describing procedures for the determination of chemical emissions from materials for interior use and requiring the use of emission test chambers, such as EN 16516, EN 16402, EN 16738, ISO 16000 series, ISO 12219 series. They all have similar QA/QC requirements in common and recommend the use of external references. With the validation data acquired in this project the total uncertainty of measurement results obtained with the test chamber method was determined and published in form of reporting documents to the respective standardisation committees for use in upcoming revision work.

The consortium faced the problem that the relevant committees either met very rarely or not at all during the project period. Every meeting that took place was used to report on project results or information was sent by email to the secretariat and the convenor of the committees if no meetings had taken place.

In June 2021, June and October 2022, the project informed CEN/TC 351/WG 2 on the project's progress at its regular meetings. In April and September 2022, as well as in September 2023 ISO/TC 146 SC 6/WG 3 was informed about the activities of the project. The feedback was very positive, particularly with regard to future exploitation routes after completion of the project. As meetings in other addressed committees, i.e., CEN/TC 421 and CEN/TC 437, did not take place, the respective chairpersons were actively contacted and informed in May 2023.

The project's outcome that might be relevant to the targeted standardisation committees is reported in detail in six deliverable reports, which were made available to them for their work.

Longer-term economic, social and environmental impacts

The project aimed to support the longer-term market position of European manufacturers of low-emitting products through the availability of better reference materials and hence increased reliability of testing. For the first time, primary gas standards (gPRM) are available for the EN 16516 check standard, which can be used to certify secondary gas standards and would therefore be available to the global network of testing institutes. Together with the candidate ERMs developed in this project, strong reference products are available that promote improved comparability of emission test results. Although the best results with ERMs in terms of a stable emission profile have so far only been achieved with two porous materials for *n*-hexadecane and μ -

capsules filled with D-limonene, the way has been paved for further development by, e.g., other research institutes.

Once, the declaration of emission data for CE marking is mandatory, more reliable testing will also increase consumer confidence in the product and the manufacturer, and thus increase sales. A similar effect on voluntary evaluation schemes that help consumers make decisions when choosing low-emitting products is also expected. Moreover, an improved comparability in emissions tests strengthens customers' trust in these labels, promotes fair competition between manufacturers, and safeguards the European common market in future building products.

The improvement of the metrological infrastructure in the field of materials emissions testing supports the long-term European harmonisation of the health-based evaluation of indoor emissions from construction products regulated by the CPR. This will support a higher level of consumer protection and should improve the health and well-being of the citizens. Furthermore, the results of this project might give additional impetus to those European member states that still are in the early stages of implementing an infrastructure for emissions testing, such as Slovenia.

- Press release “BAM develops reference material for better indoor air”, published on 4 November 2021
- Publication in professional press: “Bessere Luft in Innenräumen” (in German), published in ReinRaumTechnik, Vol. 24, January 2022

6 List of publications

de Krom, I. et al (2022) 'Metrological generation of SI-traceable gas-phase standards and reference materials for (semi-) volatile organic compounds', *Measurement Science and Technology*, 34 p. 35018. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6501/aca704>

This list is also available here: <https://www.euramet.org/repository/research-publications-repository-link/>